

Teachers' Classroom Management Practice and Instructional Competence as Correlates of Students' Academic Achievement in Chemistry

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Abstract

The main aim of the study was to find out the bond that exist among teachers' classroom management practices, teachers' instructional competences and chemistry students' academic achievement in public secondary schools in Gusau. The study was guided by five research questions and five null hypotheses. Correlational research design was used for this study. The population for the study was 38 chemistry teachers and 1,102 SS3 Chemistry Students' from the 25 Public Secondary Schools in Gusau L.G.A of Zamfara State. The sample size for the study was 313 which consisted all the 38 chemistry teachers and 275 chemistry students. Simple random sampling and purposive sampling techniques were used to select the chemistry students and teachers respectively. The three instruments: questionnaire for teachers' classroom management practice (QTCMP), questionnaire for teachers' instructional competence (QTIC) and chemistry achievement test (CAT) were used for data collection. CAT was subjected to both face and content validation, while, QTCMP and QTIC were face validated only. The instruments were reliable based on the internal consistency coefficients of 0.53, 0.88 and 0.85 when computed using Cronbach Alfa and Kuder Richardson 20 respectively. Regression Statistics was used to answer the research questions and test the hypotheses. Results showed that there was a direct positive relationship between the predictor variables (chemistry teachers' classroom discipline management practices; chemistry teachers' teaching methodologies, instructional supervision, supportive feedback, and instructional competences) and the criterion variable (students' academic achievement in chemistry). Although, the predictor variables form a bond with the criterion variable but, no statistically significant relationship among them. It was recommended among other things that chemistry teachers should manage their classrooms well to enable better improvement in students' academic achievement in chemistry.

Keywords: Teachers Classroom Management Practices, Instructional Competences, Students' Academic Achievement, and Secondary School Chemistry

Introduction

Science Education is targeted at developing scientifically literate individuals for adequate understanding of the nature of science and awareness of the relationship between science, technology and society. In the light of this fact, it is the goals of science education as enshrined in National Policy on Education (FRN, 2014): to cultivate inquiring, knowing and rational mind for the conduct of a good life and democracy; produce scientists for national development; service studies in technology and the cause of technological development; and provide knowledge and understanding of the complexity of the physical world, the forms and the conduct of life. To achieve this goal, chemistry is recommended as one of the science subjects taking by senior secondary school students at senior level in the Nigerian secondary schools (NERDC, 2013). And, a requirement for further learning of a number of science-related professional courses like medicine, agriculture, pharmacy, laboratory e.t.c. Today, Chemistry has pervaded literally every field of human endeavour, and plays a fundamental role in educational advancement.

Despite the relevance of chemistry to individual and society, Fehintola (2017) reported that academic achievement of students in chemistry in both internal and external examinations remains a problem (or a challenge) facing the educational system in Nigeria of today. Yearly, there has always been wide cry by students' each time WAEC or NECO releases their annual results (Salami, Mohammed, Ogunlade, & Ayinla, 2018) with chemistry been one of the poorest. Nevertheless, academic achievement remains and has long been recognized as the only way to measure the attainment of educational objectives in schools throughout whole world. Achievement is a result – oriented construct that shows the extent of attainment in a learning task. Academic achievement is

referred to as the knowledge attained or skills developed in the school subjects, usually determined by test scores or marks assigned by the teacher (Mirabelli, 2009). Academic achievement is also seen as a measure of the behaviour exhibited by an individual, which is noticeable after undergoing a programme in an institution or a school. This could be done in terms of teacher made test or external examination, the test could be written or oral act. The result of the demonstrated knowledge in the test, is called achievement, which will show the extent to which the objectives of the program has been achieved by the students. Determinants of academic achievement in chemistry as reported by Ojukwu, (2016) include: teachers' qualification, method of teaching, teaching experience, and use of instructional materials. These determinant mentioned hinges on teachers, to imply that, how teacher manage the class might have some effect on students learning and achievement. And by extension, the observed poor academic achievement in secondary schools' chemistry in Gusau, Zamfara State, perhaps, could be as a result of poor teachers' classroom management practices. The study of Akintola (2021) and Suleiman et. al. (2021) strengthens this proposition to necessitate this present study, as their studies revealed the state of secondary school teachers and classrooms within Gusau metropolis.

Teachers' classroom management has been defined broadly as any action a teacher takes to create an environment that supports and facilitates both academic and social-emotional learning (Evertson & Weinstein, 2006). This implies that, there are set of procedures or practices that can support the classroom learning environment, encourage appropriate behavior, and reduce the occurrence of inappropriate behavior such as fighting and noise making. In Brophy (2006), these classroom procedures are called classroom management practices. This includes: Classroom discipline, Instructional

supervision, Instructional methodologies, Supportive feedback.

Classroom discipline refers to regulation of students and maintenance of order (rules) in Classroom. Students are hereby subjected to these rules. The rules, may, for example, define the expected standards of clothing, time keeping, social behavior and work ethics. Thus, a disciplined student is that student whose behaviors, actions and inactions are accordance with the predetermined rules and regulations of the school (Ali, et al. as cited in Simba, Agak, & Kabuka, 2016) where classroom is an integral part. The next is instructional supervision, according to Akinfolarin, Babalola, & Aladetan (2017), this implies overseeing the work of teachers with the aim of assisting them to solve their instructional problems so that students can benefit maximally from classroom activities.

Instructional methodologies refer to the various ways or processes by which interaction between teachers and students can be beneficial and lead to learning. They are the procedures or set of techniques selected by the teacher/instructor to help learners experience the message that the teacher wants to put across. While, supportive feedback encompasses a variety of teachers' reaction to students' behavior such as teacher praise, correction, and affirmation of correct response. It refers to information given to the students by the teacher following a practice attempt for a skill being learned.

It is clearer therefore that, classroom management practices are beyond controlling and disciplining students. It is all the things a teacher must do in the classroom to foster students' academic involvement and cooperation in classroom activities as to create conducive learning environment. According to Wisethrithong, Sirisuthi, & Weangsamoot (2012), teacher classroom management practices is the process of enhancing the learning environment, physical interaction

between teachers and students or student to student, stimulating and motivating students to learn, control and encourage co-operation in teaching and learning activities in the classroom. In the same vein, Morse (2012) opined that classroom management practices involve curtailing learner's behaviors, close observation, arrangement of classroom learning materials, and response to students who suffer from poor sight (vision), poor reading, poor writing, poor spelling, shame, dullness, hyperactivity and poor study habits.

Apart from teachers' classroom management practices, teachers' instructional competence is another factor of concern to this study. Teachers' instructional competence is an integrated set of teachers' characteristics, knowledge, skills and attitudes that are needed for effective performance in various teaching contexts. Borich (2000) opined that teacher instructional competence is an extremely complex phenomenon that is made up of both behaviour and knowledge. Therefore, in order to measure the instructional competence of teachers: instructional planning, subject matter knowledge, learning environment, instructional strategies and student assessment are factors to be considered.

Instructional planning is the process by which teacher uses appropriate curricula, instructional strategies, resources and data during the planning process to address the diverse needs of students. Subject-matter knowledge is the knowledge and understanding of the facts, concepts, and principles and how they are organized, as well as knowledge about the discipline (Ogundeji, et. al. 2021). Learning environment is the diverse physical locations, contexts, and cultures in which students learn. Instructional strategies are the techniques teachers use to help students become independent and strategic learners. These strategies become learning strategies when students independently select the appropriate ones

and use them effectively to accomplish tasks or meet goals. Lastly, student assessment is the process of gathering and evaluating the gap between knowledge rendered and knowledge retained in relation to objective of the classroom (Aikens & Barbarin, 2008).

From the foregoing, it is obvious that there exists a connection among how a teacher manages a class, the teaching and learning process, and students' learning outcome. Marzano and Pickering (2003) noted that effective teaching and learning of chemistry cannot take place in a poorly managed classroom. Because, promotion of independent learning and success for all students in a classroom may directly or indirectly depend on effective teachers' classroom management practices which are productive, orderly and pleasant (Pederson-Seelye, 2011). The connection among teachers' classroom management practice, students' concentration, self-regulated learning, autonomy and responsibility, moral and social development have been studied (Lewis, et. al. 2012). And, Instructional competences was seen to form a bond with students' academic achievement (Ugbe & Agim, 2009). Also, Nbina (2012) found that relationship exist between teachers' competence and students' academic performance in chemistry. Teachers competence is obvious when teachers managed their classrooms well. Abdullahi (2018) reported that classroom discipline is obviously linked to teachers' ability to set an appropriate tone and gain learners' respect and cooperation in class. Simba et. al (2016) studies indicated that enhancement of classroom discipline promotes pupil's academic performance. In Akinfolarin, et. al. (2017), instructional supervision had positive correlation to students' academic achievement. Naomi, (2016) reported that academic achievement of students had a positive correlation with the science teachers' practice of instructional supervision in almost all the activities under

investigation. Added to this is the report of Wiggins and Mctighe (2007), who stressed that interaction between teacher and students during teaching and learning chemistry encourages the students academically. In a similar view, Lindquist (2002) reported that teaching methods has a propound effect on promoting greater mastery of the chemistry content. Also, Orluwene & Roseline (2015) indicated that students perform better or reached their goal when at least a little feedback on the previous performance is given. Meanwhile, Turner (2015) revealed that providing substantive feedback about competence and goal progress increases self-efficacy, enhances interest and persistence, and increases intrinsic motivation. While, non-constructive performance feedback can decrease motivation. Students who receive positive feedback are more likely to engage in learning activities and initiate positive with the teacher interactions than those who receive negative feedback.

Therefore, this study is deemed necessary since no study within the reach of researchers had reported the connection among teachers Classroom Management Practices, teachers Instructional Competences and Students' Academic Achievement, despite the poor state of secondary school teacher management and their classroom conditions especially within Gusau metropolis.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study is to determine the relationship among chemistry teachers' classroom management practices, chemistry teachers' instructional competences and students' academic achievements in chemistry.

Specifically, this study intends to find out:

1. The relationship between chemistry teachers' classroom discipline and students' academic achievement in chemistry.
2. The relationship between chemistry teachers' instructional supervision and

students' academic achievement in chemistry.

3. The relationship between chemistry teachers' classroom instructional methodologies and students' academic achievement in chemistry.
4. The relationship between chemistry teachers' supportive feedback and students' academic achievement in chemistry.
5. The relationship between chemistry teachers' instructional competences and students' academic achievement in chemistry.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the relationship between chemistry teacher classroom discipline and students' academic achievement in chemistry?
2. What is the relationship between chemistry teacher instructional supervision and students' academic achievement in chemistry?
3. What is the relationship between chemistry teacher classroom instructional methodologies and students' academic achievement in chemistry?
4. What is the relationship between chemistry teacher supportive feedback and students' academic achievement in chemistry?
5. What is the relationship between chemistry teacher instructional competences and students' academic achievement in chemistry?

Methodology

Correlational research design was used for this study. This design was selected because correlational research design was very useful in identifying relationships among the studied variables, i.e. teachers' classroom management practices, instructional competences and students' academic achievement in chemistry. Ogundeji, et al. (2021), and

Madu, et. al. (2020) have used this design in similar studies. This study was conducted in public secondary schools in Gusau, Zamfara state. The study location was chosen because it was established that there exists low level of academic achievement of students in chemistry in this area. The population for the study was 38 chemistry teachers and 1,102 SS3 Chemistry Students' of the 2020/2021 session from the 25 Public Secondary Schools in Gusau L.G.A of Zamfara State (Zamfara State Ministry of Science and Technology, 2021). The sample size for the study were 313, which consisted all the 38 chemistry teachers and 275 chemistry students. Simple random sampling and purposive sampling techniques were used to select the chemistry students and teachers respectively.

The three instruments namely: Questionnaire on Teachers Classroom Management Practices (QTCMP), Questionnaire on Teachers Instructional Competences (QTIC) and Chemistry Achievement Test (CAT) used for data collection were subjected to Validation. QTCMP which contains two sections. Section one contains demographic information and section two contain four clusters A-D. Cluster A has 7 items, cluster B and C has 8 items each, while cluster D has 5 items. It was designed on a four-point scale having the following responses: Strongly Agree, Agree, Disagree and Strongly Disagree. The second instrument QTIC contains two sections. Section A contains demographic information and section B contains three clusters A, B and C. Cluster A has 20 items; Cluster B has 10 items and cluster C has 7 items. It was also designed using a four-point scale with the following responses: Strongly Agree, Agree, Disagree and Strongly Disagree. The third instruments CAT has 20 multiple choice questions with option A to D. CAT was subjected to both face and content validation, while, QTCMP and QTIC were face validated only. For face validity, three

copies of the instrument were presented to three (3) experts: two in chemistry education from the Department of Science Education, and one from measurement and evaluation unit under the Department of Educational Foundation, Federal University Gusau, Zamfara State. Corrections given by the experts were promptly rectified during the final draft of the instrument. Likewise, the content validation was done using a test-blue print. The instruments were reliable based on the internal consistency coefficients of 0.53, 0.88 and 0.85 obtained after computation

using Cronbach Alfa and Kuder Richardson 20 respectively. Direct delivery method was used for data collection i.e. the research assistance administers and collect the responded 313 copies of the instruments back at the same spot. Meanwhile, the researchers had earlier sought for permission from the school heads before the administration of the instruments. Coefficient of determination, which is an aspect of linear regression, was used to answer the research questions while t-test was used to test the null hypotheses at 5percent probability level.

Results

Research Question 1

What is the relationship between chemistry teachers' classroom discipline management practice and students' academic achievement in chemistry?

Table 1: Regression of the relationship between Chemistry Teachers' Classroom Discipline Management Practice and Students' Academic Achievement

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.223	.049	.048	.7932519

R = correlation coefficient; R^2 = coefficient of determination

To answer this research question, the scores from the responses of the teachers on teachers' classroom discipline management behaviour were correlated with students' academic achievement in chemistry. The result in Table 1 shows that the correlation coefficient obtained was 0.223. This means that, there exist a direct relationship between teachers' classroom discipline management practice and students' academic achievement in chemistry. Table 1 also shows that, the coefficient of

determination (R^2) associated with the correlation coefficient of 0.223 was 0.049. This coefficient of determination (R^2) indicates that, 4.9% teachers' classroom discipline management practice accounted for students' academic achievement in chemistry. This is an indication that 95.1% of the variation in students' academic achievement in chemistry is attributed to other factors other than teachers' classroom discipline management practice.

Research Question 2

What is the relationship between chemistry teacher instructional supervision and students' academic achievement in chemistry?

Table 2: Regression of the relationship between Chemistry Teachers' Instructional Supervision and Students' Academic Achievement in Chemistry

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.244	.059	.058	.7932505

R = correlation coefficient; R^2 = coefficient of determination

The result from Table 2 above showed that, the scores from the responses of the teachers on teachers' instructional supervision were correlated with students' academic achievement in chemistry. The result shows that the correlation coefficient obtained was 0.244. This means that, there exist a direct relationship between teachers' classroom discipline management practice and students' academic achievement in chemistry. Table 2 also shows that, the

coefficient of determination (R^2) associated with the correlation coefficient of 0.244 was 0.059. This coefficient of determination (R^2) indicates that, 5.9% teachers' classroom instructional supervision accounted for students' academic achievement in chemistry. This is an indication that 94.1% of the variation in students' academic achievement in chemistry is attributed to other factors other than teachers' instructional supervision.

Research Question 3

What is the relationship between chemistry teacher classroom instructional methodologies and students' academic achievement in chemistry?

Table 3: Regression of the relationship between Chemistry Teachers' Classroom Instructional Methodologies and Students' Academic Achievement in Chemistry

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.223	.049	.048	.7932519

R = correlation coefficient;

R^2 = coefficient of determination

From the above table 3, the scores from the responses on teachers' classroom instructional methodologies were correlated with students' academic achievement in chemistry. The result shows a correlation coefficient of 0.223. This means that, there exist a direct relationship between teachers' classroom instructional methodologies and students' academic achievement in chemistry. The result also shows that, the coefficient of determination

(R^2) associated with the correlation coefficient of 0.223 was 0.049. This coefficient of determination (R^2) indicates that, 4.9% teachers' classroom instructional methodologies accounted for students' academic achievement in chemistry. This is an indication that 95.1% variation in students' academic achievement in chemistry is attributed to other factors other than teachers' classroom instructional methodologies.

Research Question 4

What is the relationship between chemistry teacher supportive feedback and students' academic achievement in chemistry?

Table 4: Regression of the Relationship between Chemistry Teachers' Supportive Feedback and Students' Academic Achievement in Chemistry

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.290	.084	.082	.7916410

R = correlation coefficient;

R^2 = coefficient of determination

Table 4 showed a correlation coefficient of 0.290 meaning that, a direct relationship exists between teachers' supportive feedback and students' academic

achievement in chemistry. Also, the coefficient of determination (R^2) associated with the correlation coefficient of 0.290 was 0.084. This indicated that 8.4%

chemistry teachers' supportive feedback accounted for students' academic achievement in chemistry. This implies further that 91.6% variation in students'

academic achievement in chemistry is attributed to other factors other than teachers' supportive feedback.

Research Question 5

What is the relationship between chemistry teacher instructional competences and students' academic achievement in chemistry?

Table 5: Regression of the Relationship between Chemistry Teachers' Instructional Competences and Students' Academic Achievement in Chemistry

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.530	.281	.216	.7705

r = correlation coefficient; R^2 = coefficient of determination

The result showed a correlation coefficient of 0.530. This means that, there exist a direct relationship between teachers' classroom instructional methodologies and students' academic achievement in chemistry. The result also showed that, the coefficient of determination (R^2) associated with the correlation coefficient was 0.281. This coefficient of determination (R^2)

indicated that, 28.1% teachers' instructional competences accounted for students' academic achievement in chemistry. This is an indication that 71.9% of the variation in students' academic achievement in chemistry is attributed to other factors other than teachers' classroom instructional methodologies

Discussion of Results

From the data collected for this study on teachers' classroom management practices and their instructional competences as correlates of student academic achievement in chemistry in Senior Secondary School of Gusau, Zamfara State, a number of findings have been made. From the analysis of the research questions and tests of the hypotheses, there is evidence that teachers' classroom management practices and teachers' instructional competences associated with academic achievement of students in chemistry.

The findings of the study revealed, there exist a relationship between teacher classroom discipline management practices and students' academic achievement in chemistry. Although there is an association/bond between the two variables but their relationship was not statistically significant. This current finding support those of studies by Simba et. al (2016)

among pupils in public primary schools in Muhoroni Sub-County, Kenya and Abdullahi, (2018) among Basic Science Education in the Nigeria Schools. Simba et. al (2016) studies indicated that discipline play a significant role in the improvement of academic performance of pupils and recommends the enhancement of discipline in schools. Also, the findings of Abdullahi, (2018) stressed that classroom discipline is obviously linked to teachers' ability to set an appropriate tone and gain learners' respect and cooperation in class. Teacher who has been the main force and the last person that ensure implementation of curriculum according to specification, his success or failure of actualizing instructional objectives depend to a large extent and ability of good classroom discipline. It implies that, when chemistry teachers discipline management practice is improved, it will strengthen the bond

between teachers' discipline management practice and students' academic achievement.

Finding from table 2 revealed that, there exist a direct positive relationship between chemistry teacher instructional supervision and students' academic achievement in chemistry, but their relationship was not significant. This implies that, chemistry teacher instructional supervision has a bond with students' academic achievement. But, from the data collected on the field, this bond is not clear, perhaps, the level of influence is low. Finding of this study is consistent with the findings of Akinfolarin, Babalola, & Aladetan (2017), who affirmed that instructional supervision had positive correlation to students' academic achievement. Hence, students' academic achievement in examination can be attributed to the level of supervision of teachers for effectiveness in secondary schools. Also, findings of Naomi (2016), buttressed the finding of the study that academic achievement of students had a positive correlation with the science teachers' practice of instructional supervision in almost all the activities under investigation.

In table 3, finding of the study revealed that there exists a direct positive relationship between chemistry teacher classroom instructional methodologies and students' academic achievement in chemistry, but that this relationship is insignificant. It implies that, chemistry teachers' classroom instructional methodologies had little influence on students' academic achievement in chemistry. This finding is consistent with the findings of Wiggins and Mctighe (2007) to support the fact that, interaction between teacher and students during the teaching and learning chemistry encourages the students academically, either by searching for knowledge rather than the

teacher monopolizing the transmission of information to the learners. In a similar study by Lindquist (2002), finding shows that teaching methods has a propound effect on promoting greater mastery of the subject. Application of teacher-centered methods in teaching chemistry produced results that were significantly lower comparative to those derived when using teacher-student interactive and student-centered approaches. This confirms that teacher classroom instructional methodologies form a bond with students' academic achievement in chemistry.

In table 4, findings of the study showed there exist a direct positive relationship between chemistry teacher supportive feedback and students' academic achievement in chemistry, but the relationship is not significant. This finding is consistent with the reports of Oruwene & Roseline (2015) which indicated that students perform better or reached their goal when at least a little feedback on the previous performance is given. That is effective feedback is directional and guidance-oriented for future performance and aimed at improving learning. Also, Turner (2015) revealed that providing substantive feedback about competence and goal progress increases self-efficacy, enhances interest and persistence, and increases intrinsic motivation. Conversely, non-constructive performance feedback can decrease motivation. Students who receive positive feedback are more likely to engage in learning activities and initiate positive with the teacher interactions than those who receive negative feedback. This confirms that teacher supportive feedback forms a bond with students' academic achievement in chemistry.

Lastly, findings of the study as shown in table 5 revealed that there exists a direct positive relationship

between teacher instructional competences and students' academic achievement in chemistry, but the relationship is not significant. This finding consistent with the findings of Ugbe & Agim (2009), who revealed that there is a significant influence between instructional competencies and student academic achievement. Also, Nbina (2012) found that, relationship exist between teachers' competence and students' academic performance in chemistry. He further stressed that chemistry students taught by qualified teachers performed significantly better than those taught by unqualified teachers. Also, chemistry students taught by experienced teachers performed significantly better than those taught by inexperienced teachers.

Conclusion

It is obvious that classroom management practices and teachers' instructional competences forms a bond with students' academic achievement in chemistry. Meaning that, appropriate classroom management practices and teachers' instructional competences will continue to promote students' academic achievement in chemistry. As such, inappropriate classroom management practices (such as classroom discipline, instructional supervision and methodologies, supportive feedback) should be discouraged to avert students' indiscipline such poor attitude to learning, disobedience, lateness to classrooms, rudeness to teacher, absenteeism, illogical feedback, and reinforcement of negative attitude to classroom. Also, teachers' instructional competence (such as instructional planning, subject matter

knowledge, learning environment, instructional strategies and students' assessment) should be enhanced and reinforced in secondary school chemistry especially in Gusau, since, it forms a positive bond with students' academic achievement.

Recommendations

In light of the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Chemistry teachers should be disciplined in their interactions with students especially during instructional delivery. They should set some standards for classroom control towards a better classroom conduct.
2. Chemistry teachers should be supervised by their subject head. They should check and correct their instructional aids and supervised their classroom activities.
3. Chemistry teachers should learn methodology that would give room for classroom interaction with their students for a better improvement in student academic achievement in chemistry.
4. Chemistry teachers should learn various ways of reinforcing or supporting students' positive feedback (i.e. correct behavior/response) in classroom for a better learning environment.
5. Chemistry teachers should improve on their instructional competences (especially in their pedagogical content knowledge, instructional planning and students' assessment techniques) to enhance students' academic achievement in secondary school chemistry.

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